

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING GAMES IN EFL LESSONS

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Abstract. This paper addresses the significant role of games in learning foreign languages, highlighting their pedagogical value. It emphasizes that incorporating games into lessons is crucial for achieving the teacher's educational objectives.

Key words: rapid development, government attention, interactive methods, educational games, linguistic games, game classification

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada chet tillarini o'rganishda o'yinlarning muhim roli ko'rib chiqiladi, ularning pedagogik ahamiyati ta'kidlanadi. O'qituvchining ta'lim maqsadlariga erishishda o'yinlarning darslarga kiritilishi samarali ekanligi ta'kidlanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: jadal rivojlanish, davlat e'tibori, interfaol usullar, ta'lim o'yinlari, lingvistik o'yinlar, o'yinlarning tasnifi.

Аннотация. В этой статье рассматривается важная роль игр в изучении иностранных языков, подчеркивается их педагогическая ценность. Подчеркивается, что включение игр в уроки имеет решающее значение для достижения образовательных целей учителя.

Ключевые слова: быстрое развитие, внимание правительства, интерактивные методы, образовательные игры, лингвистические игры, классификация игр.

Introduction. In our country, the fields of foreign language learning and teaching are rapidly evolving. Consequently, there is a growing demand for highly qualified specialists, prompting the government to prioritize foreign language education, as clearly outlined in recent governmental decrees. To enhance oral communication skills in foreign language instruction, the use of various interactive methods can make language learning both engaging and enjoyable. Educational games, in particular, are effective tools for improving students' speaking abilities and overall classroom effectiveness. Experience shows that games stimulate creativity in language learning, enabling students to think and communicate in the target language. In every society, games serve as a means to simulate real-life situations, allowing individuals to practice essential life skills and navigate societal challenges. They are an integral part of our culture and have long been recognized as effective tools in foreign language didactics.

Moreover, games can be utilized as gap fillers or during lighter class periods, providing a break from more intensive learning content while still fostering language acquisition. Games play a crucial role in helping teachers create contexts where language becomes both useful and meaningful. While games are often associated with fun, it is essential to recognize their significant pedagogical value, especially in the realm of foreign language teaching and learning. They effectively foster motivation, reduce student stress, and provide learners with opportunities for authentic communication.

Literature review. As J. Hadfield states, "a game is an activity with rules, a goal, and an element of fun." This definition underscores the importance of games as an integral component of the language syllabus. It illustrates that games are not merely entertaining activities; rather, they serve as valuable tools for achieving various educational objectives.

Classifying games can be challenging due to the overlapping nature of categories. J. Hadfield suggests two primary classifications for language games: linguistic and communicative. Linguistic games emphasize accuracy—such as identifying the correct antonym—while communicative games focus on the successful exchange of information and ideas.

Additionally, Hadfield proposes a more detailed classification of language games that includes categories like sorting, ordering, arranging, information gap games, guessing games, matching games, labeling, and exchanging games, as well as board games and role play.

W. Lee expands on this by identifying ten categories of games: structure games that provide experience with specific syntactical patterns in communication; vocabulary games that concentrate primarily on words; spelling and pronunciation games; number games; listen-and-do games; writing games; miming and role play; and discussion games.

Main part. *Games promote learner interaction:* Games foster interaction among learners, which is essential for effective classroom pedagogy and behavior. Pair and group work are key strategies for enhancing cooperation, and many games are designed to be played in pairs or small groups. This setup not only encourages collaboration but also helps students develop vital interpersonal skills, such as politely disagreeing and asking for assistance. In a classroom setting, learners are more likely to engage actively in these activities. Working in pairs or groups makes them more inclined to ask questions, communicate, and discuss topics with their peers, while also thinking creatively about how to use the foreign language to achieve their objectives. The competitive element of games naturally encourages students to collaborate and communicate extensively with one another.

Games Enhance Language Acquisition: The motivation and interaction generated by games significantly enhance learners' language acquisition. Students often acquire knowledge more quickly and effectively through games than through traditional methods. The desire to win stimulates and encourages participation, making the learning process enjoyable. As students engage in gameplay, they realize the necessity of using the target language for effective communication, reinforcing their learning in a practical context. Furthermore, games help to reduce anxiety. The relaxed and enjoyable atmosphere created by game-based activities allows students to remember information more easily and effectively. The meaning of the language that students listen to, read, speak, and write becomes more vividly experienced within the context of a game, leading to improved retention of the language.

Games Increase Learner Achievement: Games can incorporate all four fundamental language skills: listening, speaking, reading, and writing, often engaging multiple skills simultaneously. By motivating learners and promoting interaction, games can enhance overall achievement. This translates into improved test results, better communication abilities, expanded vocabulary knowledge, and other essential language skills.

Example of a Classroom Game: "Sunflower". One game I frequently use in my lessons is called "Sunflower." In this activity, students are divided into groups of 4-5 individuals. Based on a specific science topic, I present a problem for discussion. Each group forms a "sunflower" by creating a circle with their members and adding leaves around the center. Each group writes a common problem related to the topic on a leaf and sticks it on the board. Within a set timeframe, groups collaboratively brainstorm their thoughts on the issue and write them down on their respective leaves. These leaves are then placed on the sunflower with the

problem written on it. This method not only encourages teamwork but also reinforces the topic being studied, allowing me to assess the knowledge acquired by the students effectively.

In the next game, participants will work in pairs. The first participant will introduce themselves in the foreign language by stating their name, while the second participant will repeat the first participant's name and then add their own. For example:

- First student: "My name is Jeremie."

- Second student: "His name is Jeremie, and my name is Nicole."

This pattern continues as each student takes their turn. At the beginning of the school year, introducing such games can help students get acquainted with one another. Through this activity, they practice speaking English with each other while also testing the strength of their memories.

Conclusion. Games are a valuable tool in language teaching. They not only motivate learners and create a friendly atmosphere but also focus on developing all language skills. As a result, games foster interaction among learners, enhance their language acquisition, and ultimately improve their academic performance. In summary, games can be an effective teaching tool. A successful game is characterized by specific time allocation, clear relevance to the material being taught, inclusivity for all class members, and an increase in learner enjoyment through active engagement with the language.

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